

QUIZ**LAST NAME: KELLY****FIRST NAME: WILLIAM****PROGRAM CODE: DIPH****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR GULMA**

The author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.
The author used Turabian (footnotes)
The author did not use Zotero to insert all references
The author used the following software: (MSWord 2016 on Windows 10)

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

1. **Which two features, typify academic essay writing?**

- Descriptive and Analytical.
- Strategic and Symbolic.
- Technical and Systematic.
- Creative and Critical.¹**

2. **Which of the following statements in a more accurate description of a dissertations' abstract: An abstract is,**

- A carefully worded summary, which precedes the body of the work, that informs the reader of what to expect.²**
- An esoteric statement in which you outline the inquiries ontology.

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, 2nd edition (Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2019), 2.

² Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap from Beginning to End* (Los Angeles: Sage Publications, 2008), 168.

- An exposition concerning epistemological intent.
 - A justification of the inquiries axiological position.
3. **In their approach to an inquiry setting, which of the following best describes the type of questions which researchers conventionally ask?**
- Critical, Analytical, Reflexive.
 - Insightful, Meaningful, Valuable.
 - Plausible, Methodical, Useful.
 - Conceptual, Practical, Applied.**³
4. **Which statement is the most accurate, completion of the following the sentence: The purpose of a literature review is to**
- Show what you know about, the topic/problem.
 - Identify what is already known on, the topic/problem.**⁴
 - Highlight what is unknown about, the topic/problem.
 - Reveal what is intended to be known about the topic/problem.
5. **Which answer supports the claim that readers of dissertations, expect dissertations to have the following;**
- Introduction, Literature Review, Theory Framework, Research Design, Data Analysis, Bibliography.

³ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, 8th edition., Chicago guides to writing, editing, and publishing (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013), 15-17.

⁴ Bloomer and Volpe, 18-19

- Introduction, Research Problem, Research Question, Testable Hypothesis, Analysis, Recommendations.
 - Introduction, Methods, Materials, Results, Discussion, Conclusions.**⁵
 - Introduction, Research Plan, Interview Data, Results, Conclusions, References.
6. **Which answer is the most reasonable completion of the following sentiment: A selected bibliography enables a researcher to**
- Select what they think should or should not be in the references.
 - Adjudicate references based on importance.
 - Select only the authors which they think, should be included.
 - With institutional oversight, to omit the inclusion of uninteresting or and minor works.**⁶
7. **What is the most accurate completion of the following sentence: The academic community considers plagiarism to be**
- Symbolic of poor scholarship.
 - Acceptable, but only under exceptional circumstances.
 - Understandable, in that students are only learning.
 - Wrong, unethical, and, a serious academic offence.**⁷
8. **What are the three fundamental elements of a researchers argument**

⁵ Kate L. Turabian, 43

⁶ Kate L. Turabian, 93.

⁷ Euclid, 5.

- Transferability and Generalisability and Justifiability.
 - Credibility and Reliability and Triangulation,
 - Claim and Reason and Evidence.**⁸
 - Being right, knowing your right, and proving you were right.
9. **Complete the following sentence: In light of the quantity of data collected in a qualitative inquiry, qualitative data analysis is the process of bringing some**
- Organisation, and clarity, and purpose, to the data.
 - Intellect, and elucidation, and relevance, to the data.
 - Order, and structure, and meaning, to the data.**⁹
 - Value, and transparency, and importance, to the data.
10. **Data reduction and data display are aspects of which, of the following.**
- Data Management.
 - Data Storage.
 - Data Analysis.**¹⁰
 - Data Coding.

⁸ Kate L. Turabain, 37.

⁹ Bloomberg and Volpe, 96.

¹⁰ Bloomberg and Volpe, 99.

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